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Thermochemical Studies of some Lanthanide Acetates

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THE lanthanides together with yttrium display predominantly a trivalent chemistry. Due to the resemblance in their structural, electronic and energetic characteristics, these elements are studied together. Earlier reported works¹⁻³ on thermochemical studies of lanthanide complexes are few and invite attention for a systematic probe.

In this communication, the enthalpies of combustion (ΔH_c) of some crystalline lanthanide acetates have been reported. By substituting the auxiliary thermochemical data, the standard enthalpies of formation, (ΔH_f°) of the complexes have been estimated. These data have been used in the derivation of metal-oxygen (acetate) mean bond dissociation enthalpies, $D(M-O)$.

Experimental

The lanthanide acetates of Y^{III}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Nd^{III} and Gd^{III} (99.99%; Rare Earths Limited) were used. The complexes were dried at 115–120° and desiccated. The enthalpy of combustion of each complex was found using a bomb calorimeter by burning a weighed pellet in an excess of oxygen and measuring the rise in temperature in a known quantity of water. Supporting pellet of pure benzoic acid was used along with the complex to ensure complete combustion.

Results and Discussion

The enthalpies of combustion of complexes are determined from relation,

$$\Delta H_c = M \times W \times \Delta t$$

where M is the gram molecular weight of the complex, W the water equivalent of bomb calorimeter measured as $10545 \pm 15 \text{ JK}^{-1}$ and Δt the temperature rise per gram of the sample. As the result of combustion of crystalline complexes, the following products were characterised⁴,

where $M = \text{Y, La, Nd and Gd}$, and for Ce-acetate,

For these two reactions, $\Delta H = \Delta H_c$.

All the lanthanide oxides, M_2O_3 , are readily obtained and characterised. Except for cerium, these oxides are the final products of combustion in oxygen medium of most of the complexes containing oxo ligands. At elevated temperatures, cerium(IV) oxide is readily obtainable by the ignition of cerium(III) oxide in excess of oxygen provided sufficient time is allowed for complete conversion of intermediate non-stoichiometric phases⁵.

TABLE I— ΔH_c AND ΔH_f° VALUES FOR SOME LANTHANIDE ACETATES

Compd.	M g	Δt °C g ⁻¹	ΔH_c kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_f° kJ mol ⁻¹
Y(CH ₃ COO) ₃	265.9	0.877 ± 0.006	-2 459 ± 15	-2 127
La(CH ₃ COO) ₃	315.9	0.715 ± 0.004	-2 382 ± 10	-2 162
Ce(CH ₃ COO) ₃	317.1	0.745 ± 0.005	-2 498 ± 10	-2 237
Nd(CH ₃ COO) ₃	321.2	0.710 ± 0.003	-2 405 ± 07	-2 147
Gd(CH ₃ COO) ₃	334.2	0.689 ± 0.004	-2 428 ± 10	-2 127

The standard enthalpies of formation of complexes (Table 1) are estimated,

$$\Delta H_f^\circ M(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3(c) = 1/2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{M}_2\text{O}_3(c) + 6 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CO}_2(g) + 9/2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{H}_2\text{O}(l) - \Delta H_c$$

where $M = \text{Y, La, Nd and Gd}$, and for Ce-acetate,

$$\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Ce}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3(c) = \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CeO}_2(c) + 6 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CO}_2(g) + 9/2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{H}_2\text{O}(l) - \Delta H_c$$

The enthalpies of formation of the products which include their respective metal oxides, carbon dioxide and water in standard states have been compiled from the literature^{6,7}. The ΔH_f° values for some of the above acetates have been determined earlier³ by the use of solution calorimeter, and the presently found ones are in agreement with those reported earlier.

Metal-oxygen mean bond dissociation enthalpies in lanthanide acetates: The bond enthalpy (ΔH_b) is the enthalpy of formation of a gaseous triacetato complex,

$$\Delta H_b = \Delta H_f^\circ M(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3(g) - \Delta H_f^\circ M(g) - 3 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CH}_3\text{COO}(g)$$

since $\Delta H_f^\circ M(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3(g) = \Delta H_f^\circ M(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3(c) + \Delta H_{sub}$

The enthalpies of sublimation (ΔH_{sub}) have not been reported due to the difficulty of decomposing the complexes at elevated temperatures. However,

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fair estimates are made on the basis of similar data for lanthanide halides which vary little from each other and are in the vicinity of 300 kJ mol⁻¹. The enthalpy of formation of gaseous metal atom, $\Delta H_f^\circ M(g)$, and the gaseous acetate radical, $\Delta H_f^\circ CH_3COO(g)$, are taken from standard sources⁸. $\bar{D}(M-O)$ values (Table 2) are taken as $-\Delta H_g/6$, since carboxylates act as bidentate ligands in these complexes. The presently found $\bar{D}(M-O)$ value and other data for yttrium(III) acetate are in proximity with those derived for yttrium(III) acetylacetonate¹⁰.

TABLE 2— $\bar{D}(M-O)$ VALUES (kJ mol⁻¹) IN SOME LANTHANIDE ACETATES

Compd.	$\Delta H_f^\circ M(CH_3COO)_2(g)$	$\Delta H_f^\circ M(g)$	$-\Delta H_g$	$\bar{D}(M-O)$
Y(CH ₃ COO) ₃	-1 827	389	1 565	261
La(CH ₃ COO) ₃	-1 862	431	1 642	274
Ce(CH ₃ COO) ₃	-1 937	467	1 753	292
Nd(CH ₃ COO) ₃	-1 847	323	1 519	253
Gd(CH ₃ COO) ₃	-1 827	339	1 515	252

The results give an idea of the effect of an octahedral ligand field on the 4f electrons in the lanthanide complexes. The minima observed for various enthalpy terms in case of gadolinium complex (4f⁷) may be attributed to this effect¹¹. The ligand field stabilisation energy (LFSE) though very small in comparison to 3d transition metals, is minimum for the lanthanide ions having 4f⁰, 4f⁷ and 4f¹⁴ electronic configurations.

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Thermal, IR and XRD Studies of Ammonium-interacted Deolite

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COMMERCIAL deolite is a desiccant having similar properties as 4A type zeolites. To our knowledge commercial deolite has never been used for cation-exchange or adsorption. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to use deolite as a cation-exchanger for ion like NH₄⁺(I), and the new material has been used as an adsorbent for ammonia with a view to testing its potential for pollution control. Effect of heating up to 900° has been followed by TG analysis and ir spectroscopy. X-ray diffraction studies of the NH₄⁺-deolite and its adsorbed derivatives provide useful information on their structure as compared with those of 4A zeolites¹.

Experimental

Deolite sample (Ras Enterprises) was immersed in a saturated aqueous ammonium chloride for several days and later eluted with fresh lots of the same solution. It was then filtered and air-dried to a white exchanged sample of deolite. The sample was stored with liquor ammonia in a refrigerator.

The NH₄⁺-deolite and its adsorbed samples were subjected to TG analysis upto 900° at a heating rate of 15° min⁻¹ using a Perkin-Elmer thermobalance. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded² on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. X-Ray diffractograms were obtained between 2θ angles of 7° and 60° using CuK_α radiation of 1.5418 Å on a Phillips PW 1140 instrument. Most of the reflections were indexed for (hkl) value following reported methods³.

Results and Discussion

Deolite shows a remarkable exchange capacity with NH₄⁺ ion which replaced 80.71% of Na₂O. Such type of work was carried out by earlier workers with other zeolites.

Total weight-loss in TG analysis of NH₄⁺-exchanged deolite has been found to be 23.40%. The thermogram consists of two weight-loss steps. The first in the temperature range 60–378° with a weight-loss of 18.50% which can be attributed due to the loss of water. Partial deammoniation is also a distinct possibility as two DTG endotherms are absorbed successively around 105° and at 300–350°. The weight-loss of NH₄⁺-deolite is slightly higher than the other exchanged forms and also deolite and this extra loss can be due to deammoniation. The second weight-loss (4.90%) located beyond this temperature range, can be attributed to the breaking of OH groups or dehydroxy-